

CF/MODIFIED-PEEK COMPOSITES FOR AIRCRAFT

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ABSTRACT

When you consider heat resistance and chemical resistance of thermoplastic resins in aerospace composite materials, neither conventional PPS, PEI nor PEEK based composites can be enough. Therefore, we developed modified-PEEK resins, which resulted 20°C higher T_g than conventional PEEKs by adding high T_g polymers. In this study, we showed some properties of modified-PEEK matrix carbon fiber composites, such as mechanical property at high temperature, fluid resistance and flammability. These results indicated that the modified-PEEK composites should be acceptable for aerospace structural components.

1 INTRODUCTION

Carbon fiber reinforced plastics (CFRPs) have been applied as lightweight materials for high fuel saving in aerospace and automotive industries. Especially, carbon fiber reinforced thermoplastics (CFRTPs) have been focused on excellent properties of impact resistance, automated molding and recyclability. Recently a composite material has been adopted for a component in an aero engine of the Airbus A320 neo using an advanced thermoplastic because of its excellent impact property [1-2]. Among many advanced thermoplastics, PEI (polyetherimide) resin is one of the most popular to be applied for airplane components because of its cost, heat resistance and flammability. However, chemical resistance of PEI resins shows poor to some solvents because PEI resins are amorphous, not crystalline polymers, as shown in Table 1. So some surface treatments must be required to preserve the PEI-based composite products during long running of aircrafts. On the other hand, PEEK (polyetheretherketone) resins have great properties of chemical resistance and mechanical property, however T_g (glass transition temperature) of the resin, which indicates an index of heat resistance, is relatively low.

Matrix resin	PPS	PEI	PEEK	PEKK	Modified-PEEK
Polymer type	Crystalline	Amorphous	Semi-crystalline	Low-crystalline	Semi-crystalline
Mechanical property	+	+	++	++	++
Moldability	++	0	0	0~+	0
Heat resistance	0	+++	+	++	++
Chemical resistance	+	-	+	0	+

Table 1: Advantages and disadvantages of thermoplastic resins for aerospace application.

In order to improve heat resistance of PEEK resins, PEKK (polyetherketoneketone) resins were developed, which have 10°C higher T_g than regular PEEKs and gradually popular in aerospace industry. It is well known that commercial PEKK resins are co-polymer of two different chemical structures, not homo-polymer [3]. So T_g and T_m (melting temperature) of PEKK are various for each different type of co-polymer, as shown in Fig 1. Moreover, recently some chemical companies have developed unique modified-PEEK resin as PAEK (polyaryletherketone) to improve PEEK with higher T_g or with lower T_m , as shown in Fig 1.

Figure 1: Relationship between T_g and T_m of some thermoplastic polymers, including developed modified-PEEK in this study.

We developed modified-PEEK resin, by mixing PEEKs and high T_g polymers. Figure 2 is relationship between weight fraction of the high T_g polymers in whole polymer and T_g by dynamic mechanical analyzer (DMA- T_g) of the composites. In this figure, when the high T_g polymers contains more than “content A” in modified PEEKs, DMA- T_g of the composites are almost saturated, showing over 160°C at dry condition and over 150°C at wet condition. So we think that the “content A” is one of the appropriate compositions in modified-PEEK to keep mechanical properties of original PEEKs with 20°C higher T_g than PEEKs. In this study, we measured some properties of the modified-PEEK based composites, such as heat resistance, strength and flammability.

Figure 2: Relationship between the content of high T_g polymers in modified-PEEK and DMA- T_g of the composites, where wet condition is soaking in 70°C water in 2 weeks.

2 EXPERIMENTS

2.1 Sample procedure

We fabricated modified-PEEK based prepreg and composites with following procedure. Carbon fiber Pyrofil MR50R (Mitsubishi Chemical) was used as reinforcement fibers in the modified-PEEK prepregs. Fiber areal weight of the prepreg is 190 g/m^2 and weight fraction of polymer matrix is $33\pm 1\%$. The laminated prepregs were heated up to $380\sim 400^\circ\text{C}$ on hot platen and cooled down to 200°C on cold platen in a double platen hydraulic press, as shown in Fig 3. Cooling rate of the molding was around $100^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$. All lamination and thickness for each measurement are described in Table 2. The modified-PEEK based composites were compared with other thermoplastic and thermosetting based composites.

Figure 3: Double platen heat-and-cool press, used in this study.

	Measurement	Lamination	Thickness
Mechanical property	Temperature dependence of 90° flexural strength	UD	Approx. 2 mm
	0° tensile strength	UD	Approx. 1 mm
	90° tensile, 0° compression and 90° compression strength	UD	Approx. 2 mm
	CAI and OHC strength	Quasi-isotropic	Approx. 4.5 mm
	G_{IC} and G_{IIC}	UD	Approx. 3 mm
	Flammability	UD	Approx. 3 mm

Table 2: Lamination and thickness of all tests in this study.

2.2 Measurements

For temperature dependence of transverse flexural strength (90FS) of the composites, three-point bending tests were performed at room temperature (RT), 121 , 141 and 160°C , based on ASTM D790.

In order to obtain flammability of composites, OSU-HRR (Heat release rate) was measured by a fire instrument (RHR-1-X, Govmark) for 5 minutes as shown in Fig. 4. The fire test was based on FAR Part 25 appendix F part IV, where maximum HRR during the test and total HR at 2 minutes should be less than 65 kWmin/m^2 and 65 kW/m^2 , respectively, for aerospace applications. Following mechanical properties of PEEK and modified-PEEK based composites were compared; longitudinal (0°) and transverse (90°) tensile strength and compression strength, CAI (Compression after impact) strength by impact energy of 30 J , OHC (Open hole compression) strength, interlaminar fracture toughness of mode I (G_{IC}) and mode II (G_{IIC}). These measurements were based on corresponding ASTM standards.

Figure 4: A fire instrument for OSU heat release rate.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

3.1 Temperature dependence

Fig. 5 shows temperature dependence of the transverse flexural strength of some thermoplastic composites. The strength of the modified-PEEK composite resulted higher around 120~160°C than that of other thermoplastic composites. Especially around 140°C, which is around T_g of PEEK resin, the flexural strength of the PEEK composite decreased to 80% compared with the strength at room temperature. On the other hand, the flexural strength of the modified-PEEK composite decreased to 90%. In the case of PEI and PEKK composites with higher T_g , their transverse flexural strength drastically decreased around 120~160°C. This result can be rationalized as follows. For PEI composite, similar behavior were reported about PEI and PES (polyethersulfone) based composite [4, 5], which belong to amorphous polymers. There is a possibility that amorphous polymer based composites show the decrease of strength below their T_g s. In the case of PEKK composite, cooling rate was so rapid in molding than longtime autoclave, so the crystallization of PEKK polymer might be lower and not enough. Consequently, we showed the modified-PEEK composite has higher actual heat resistance around 120~160°C from the view point of transverse strength of composite.

Figure 5: Temperature dependence of transverse flexural strength (90FS) of thermoplastic composites, normalized by the strength of each composite at room temperature.

3.2 Mechanical properties

Compared with regular PEEK composite, strength of modified-PEEK composite showed slightly lower, such as transverse tensile strength and CAI strength in Figure 6. Before compression fracture

test of CAI, larger delamination was observed by impact in the modified-PEEK composite specimens. As above mentioned, high T_g polymers can provide higher heat resistance to modified PEEK, but can make the matrix resin relatively brittle. Nevertheless the decrease of strength was within 10% to PEEK based composite, the mechanical properties of the modified-PEEK composite show high level and will be acceptable for aircrafts.

Figure 6: Comparison of mechanical properties of the PEEK and the modified-PEEK based composites, each property is normalized by that of PEEK based composite.

3.3 Flammability

Fig. 7 shows fire test result of some thermoplastic composites. PEEK, PEI, PPS and modified-PEEK based composites with 3 mm thickness passed in FAR fire test standards, because maximum HRR and total HR at two minutes were less than 65 kW/m^2 and 65 kWmin/m^2 , respectively. In the case of commercial flame retardant epoxy composite, the specimen did not pass the fire test, because results of the test are influenced by thickness of specimen. So thinner specimen of the material may pass the test more easily. We found that flammability of the modified-PEEK composites showed almost equivalent as PEEK and PEI composites, and has higher flame retardance than PPS and thermosetting composites.

Figure 7: Maximum heat release rate during fire test and total heat release at two minutes of thermoplastic and thermosetting composites.

4 CONCLUSIONS

In this study, we can obtain following conclusions on our developed modified-PEEK composite. These results indicated that the modified-PEEK composites will be acceptable for aerospace structural components.

- Transverse flexural strength decrease to 90% around 140°C, compared with the strength at room temperature. The retention ratio in strength around the 140~160°C shows higher than other thermoplastic composites.
- Modified-PEEK based composite has 90% of CAI strength and almost same OHC strength, compared with PEEK based composite.
- Modified PEEK composite can pass the FAR fire test. The heat release rate and the total heat release from the composite showed almost equivalent as PEEK and PEI composites and lower than PPS composites.

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